

Array of synthetic jets for large passenger aircraft

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ABSTRACT:

The key challenge of flow control on aircrafts is to provide reliable power over a long period to influence the aerodynamic characteristics over the airfoil. There are several approaches and types of fluidic flow control devices. The most convenient option is the implementation of synthetic jet actuators (SJAs) in airfoil structures. In particular, SJAs based on piezoelectric materials are currently achieving promising results. All types of piezoelectric jet actuators consist of basic elements like substrate, piezoelectric transducer element and a cavity with a nozzle. Advantageous is the symmetrical composition of SJAs. Such a design has many benefits in load performance and offers a compact, space-saving installation. Each symmetrical module of SJA has a separate nozzle or cavity and generates alternating pulsed airflow without requiring pressurized air. Thus, the blowing frequency of the entire construction is twice higher than the operating frequency of the actuator. For this purpose, the novel design of SJA regarding performance and robustness is studying. The improvements for future development are derived.

1. INTRODUCTION

Aerodynamic research regarding performance, fuel efficiency and environmental friendliness is still important. Reduction of environmental impact of aircraft turbines requests new concepts, material and innovative technologies. Minimizing losses due to aerodynamic friction is an important aspect of fluid flow control. Fluid flow control can occur on different ways [1]. In the case of

active flow control, various principles for different interesting applications can be found and classified on its function [2]. For example, in [3] flow control by plasma actuators, in [4] by piezo-electric flaps and in [5] electro-mechanical driven actuators principle can be found. Another approach are synthetic jet actuators (SJAs), whose working principle is also used as micro fluidic pumps. For active fluid flow control such devices are applicable for combustion [6], jet vectoring [7], cooling [8] or controlling of boundary layers [9]. In comparison to pulsed jet devices or continuous jets, the huge benefit of synthetic jet actuators is that no additional compressed air source is needed. For that reason, SJAs can be referred as zero net mass flux devices and lead to the possibility of preventing energy and lift losses as well as changing of wall skin friction in the field of aircraft applications. The interaction effects and application for flow control is discussed in [10].

The development of the powerfully fluidic jet actuator includes stepwise solution and implementation of technical approaches. The goal is to improve existing models regarding the performance (exit velocity) and the reliability of the actuators. Last one is a significant point with respect to permanent integration of SJAs into structures. Different activities support this development. Fig. 1 shows the successive working areas for active implementation of SJA in functional surface structures:

Figure 1: Main goals for the development of the next generation fluidic actuators

2. JET ACTUATOR

The functionality of jet actuator bases on at least three components: membrane, piezo-element and housing with cavity and nozzle (see Fig. 2).

Figure 2. Schematic representation of the default setup of a jet actuator structure (single chamber concept)

This is the simplest working structure of a SJA. Dependent on the requirements the structure can be modified. However, the principle still the same, the membrane bends due to electrical signals on the attached piezoelectric element. The volume of the cavity changes corresponding to the oscillating membrane so that air jet pulses are generated through the nozzle.

For our application, the double chamber concept is chosen (Fig. 3). The advantage of symmetrical structure, beside manufacturing and economic benefits, is a two-nozzle setup with just a single membrane.

Figure 3. Schematic representation of jet actuator structure with double chamber

In most SJA structures, only one piezo-element is attached on the metallic membrane. It is more appropriate to use two piezoelectric elements (psp-structure, see Fig. 4) for the membrane. Such assembly gives much higher exploitation of the material and higher mechanical quality factor. In addition, having both piezo-elements active results in a better compensation of external influences of a psp-structure compared to a ps-structure. A good example is thermal load on the SJA. The difference between thermal expansion coefficients of ceramic and material of substrate will not affect the behavior.

Figure 4. Membrane with two piezo-elements (psp-structure)

The manufacturing of piezo ceramic disks with diameter to thickness ratio of 100 is an expensive and sensitive process. The thickness smaller than 0.2 mm is economical not reasonable. Due to the very thin thickness, these elements are sensitive to breakage. For practical purpose it is recommendable to select piezoelectric material with high coercive field strength E_c not less than 1.0 kV/mm and depending on the requirements, sufficient high Currie-temperature e.g. 280°C. On the one side, the strength of electrical field defines the driving nominal voltage or rather bending. On the other side too high bending leads to reduction of the lifetime of the piezo element. This means, a compromise between the robustness of the elements and driving voltage has to be found. For application purpose where the jet actuator shall be used in environments with temperature fluctuations, the temperature dependency of the electrical capacity of piezo-elements has to be considered during the selection process.

Before the bonding process of the piezo material and steel membrane starts, it is advisable to pretreat the surfaces. Particularly, the membrane can be pretreated by plasma to increase surface energy and to enable a reliable adhesive bond. This prevents the separation of glued materials.

Another important point is the electrical contact of piezo-elements. Contacting the electrode surface directly on the ceramic should be discouraged. The practice shows that continuous vibration weakens the solder contact and leads to failure. By means of special techniques and electro conductive ink the electrical circuits can be printed directly to the surface of piezo-elements (see Fig. 5). Whereby, the sufficient width of conducting path needs to be ensured. Such wiring concepts have different advantages and disadvantages.

Figure 5. Design concept for conductive ink/printed electrical contact

To optimize the functionality of SJA each part of the assembly (like transducer, housing, clamping, electrical connection ...) requires additional development and manufacturing. Until now, the following development steps of the transducer elements have been finished:

- Dimensioning of piezo / substrate combination
- Material selection
- Ordering of piezo / substrate material
- Pre-processing of piezo ceramics (cleaning, ...)
- Pre-processing of substrate material
- Applying adhesives
- Positioning of piezo on substrate
- Curing of adhesives

The manufacturing is attended by the analysis of each single process step. The process steps of the manufacturing is given in the Fig. 6 below.

Figure 6: Process steps for the manufacturing of the fluidic actuator

This process has been extended with additional process parameters and steps. This allows a more detailed view on each of the steps. With the help of such analysis, it is much easier to identify bottlenecks in the manufacturing steps as well as time and cost consuming processes. This activity is still ongoing and will be improved systematically.

The current setup meets the objective goals and shows a bending deflection of the transducer element of approx. $\pm 150 \mu\text{m}$ @ 150 V in mechanical resonance. If it is not necessary, the SJA has not be driven with maximum power. On the Fig. 7 the jet velocities through the nozzle of 3 mm diameter for different driving voltages is represented. The design of the cavity and nozzle shape of the SJA leads to acoustical resonance frequency of 400 Hz and mechanical resonance frequency of 1100 Hz. The measurements of the exit velocity have been done with the help of hot-wire anemometry. It can be inferred from the Fig. 7 that the highest jet speed is for mechanical resonance. In some cases it is an advantage to work in acoustical resonance, in which the noise level is much lower. In comparison to other work [11], the double chamber setup creates a higher exit velocity for the same driving voltages. This is caused by the increased diameter of the transducer element and therefore the higher deflection of the membrane. Large diameter of the membrane also decreases the resonance frequency. The optimized chamber and nozzle geometry leads to an optimal flow inside the

actuator and higher exit velocities in front of the nozzle. Both aspects are necessary to increase the field of applications.

Figure 7. Air jet speed velocity regarding frequency and driving voltage

3. MODELLING

To simplify the design of jet actuators it is helpful to use electrical analogous model of SJA. To improve the simplified model it is useful to combine network analysis and numerical calculations (finite element method, FEM). In this case, model is divided in an acoustic and an electro-mechanical part. The extraction of lumped parameters from the electromechanical part of the system occurs by finite elements. The results will be used as input for the modeling of acoustic system, which is simulated by lumped elements method (LEM). This approach was already proposed [12] and has been proved successful in earlier studies and developments of synthetic jet actuators [11].

Figure 8. Schematic diagram of combined simulation model and corresponding network model of SJA

4. ROBUSTNESS AND RELIABILITY TESTS

Long term reliability tests are used to get more information about failure modes of the actuators and their transducer elements. Another important point for a robust and reliable actuator is the influence of environmental parameters like temperature and humidity. Therefore, a new test setup has been developed. This allows a detailed view on the real actuator (piezo) behavior. The setup used for those measurements is shown in Fig. 9.

Figure 9. (a) Setup for actuator mounting inside the climatic chamber (b) deflection measurement from outside using LD vibrometer

Figure 10. Exit velocity over the measurement time of 600 h

Fig. 10 shows the exit velocity of one actuators over the time of the experiment. The results show, that the exit velocity did not change over time for this configuration. The actuator has an average exit velocity of 41 m/s. This value can be assumed to be constant over the time, as the small ripples are the result of turbulences in front of the nozzle.

Figure 11. Driving current (peak-peak) over the measurement time of 600 h

The current (peak-peak value) is also constant over time. The small ripples are just the result of the measurement accuracy as the current is very low for a single actuator. Another indicator for different failure modes is the wave form of driving voltage and current. Current spikes or an overlay of additional frequencies are the result of damages. During the tests and even after the final measurement, none of the actuators shows a strange behavior or a none-harmonic acoustic signal. This could also be verified with the wave form of the current as shown in Fig. 11 on the example of actuator driving current (peak-peak) over the measurement time of 600 h.

All of the actuators used in this experiments show a very stable behavior in terms of exit velocity and performance over time. A decrease or even loss in performance could not be verified. None of the actuators got additional damages during the tests. Although the performance differs between the actuators, a change over time could not be monitored. It has to be mentioned, that those tests have been performed in a static environment without cross flow, external loads/forces, temperature or other environmental changes.

5. INTEGRATION CONCEPT

To influence the behavior of the air flow over the wing by using SJA, an array of SJA's over the whole width of active zone is needed. The aim is to generate a formation of air jets, which can induce additional vortices on the one hand and destroy bigger vortices on the other hand. Both to improve the behavior of the flow over the surface of wing.

In the near future, an aerodynamic test with SJA is planned (Fig. 12). To cover the active zone on the wing over the pylon an array of 49 SJAs is manufactured (Fig. 13). At the moment all design parameters are known and integration of SJAs in a panel is completed. Because of the dimensions and convex/concave surfaces, the manufacturing of testing panel is a technical challenge. Only special equipped factory is capable to fabricate panel in one piece. Therefore, it was necessary to split the whole panel in shorter parts. The complete testing setup consists of 8 parts as shown in Fig. 13a. Altogether, there are 49 slots for the integration of 49 SJAs. Fig. 13b shows the backside of one part of the panel with two SJAs mounted.

Figure 12. Installation position of SJA array

a)

b)

c)

Figure 13. a) Manufactured testing panel, (b) backside view on one part of the panel with two SJAs, (c) complete panel with SJAs and electrical wiring

6. DRIVING ELECTRONIC PART

The boundary conditions during the test and in laboratory are completely different. This means that the resonance frequency or rather working point is also different. Also during tests the working point, due to different wind velocities in wind tunnel, can vary. Thus, the driving electronics should be able to readjust the operation point. Fig. 14 shows the schematic representation of such driving circuit. An ADC measures the values of current and voltage directly from SJA. Based on the current behavior, the frequency of the controller is adjusted to the working point.

Figure 14. (a) Schematic representation of electric driving circuit of SJA, (b) two racks of power amplifiers and cables

7. CONCLUSION

In a present work an array concept for the generation of pulsed air jet by the means of synthetic jet actuators was presented. A novel design in comparison to previous work [11] is shown in this paper. The concept of simplified modeling was used and tested. The manufacturing of complicated nozzle and cavity shape was made by rapid prototyping and printed circuit board technology. It could be shown, that a performance improvement was achieved by increasing the diameter of the transducer element and by optimizing the inner fluid structure of the actuator. In addition to [11], a double chamber design is capable of creating two air jets with only a single transducer

element. Means, such a design can induce more than twice the energy into the surrounding air flow than the previous generation of actuators. The performance of the novel design can be used to generate powerful jets for affect the surface flow behavior of a wing. The special design of the housing enable an integration of synthetic jet actuators directly into the wing. In the future work the tests of the SJA array is planned.

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9. REFERENCES

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